

**ADAPTIVE CONTROL METHOD FOR COMPRESSOR STABILITY
WITH NOVEL CASING TREATMENT**

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ABSTRACT

In order to avoid the instabilities (stall & surge) of compressor system, an adaptive control method has been developed and applied on compressor stabilization based on stall warning approach and a stall precursor-suppressed (SPS) casing treatment. Through this adaptive control method, the compressor stability status can be monitored in real time. Aimed at different operating and condition identifications, the SPS casing treatment can match the optimal geometric parameters to suppress the linear amplification of stall precursors and control the compressor stability.

INTRODUCTION

Plenty of efforts have been made since 50s of last century for the stability shortage of modern aero-engines, especially for the challenge of stability control. With the development of advanced aero-engines, the compressor loading and overall efficiency demands become higher and higher, so the compressor stability problem is always the major concern.

For compressor stability control, an earlier attempt is a kind of method based on dynamic feedback control which was conducted in the mid-1980s. This method that considered as active compressor stability control could enhance the stability margin of a compressor system through unsteady dynamic approach than changing the steady characteristic of compressor [1]. This active stabilization method was originated from the discovery of stall inception and developed for the suggestion of anti-sound theory. It was confirmed that the evolution process (nonlinear amplification) of stall inception could directly

lead to rotating stall, and disturbances with anti-phase generated by a certain actuator could suppress the amplification of stall inception waves. Haynes [2], Longley [3], Weigl [4] and Greitzer [5] et al. used the system identification techniques to analysis the stall-inception process in order to obtain more details of compressor unsteady flow and to get some quantitative parameters assessment of the fluid dynamic in control models. A general scheme of compressor active stabilization system usually consists some sensors (usually 4-8) mounted on the casing of one compressor stage to detect the pressure perturbations and some actuators (usually 8-12) to reject the perturbation harmonic of different orders. All these parts establish a typical feedback control system. Experiments showed that the first order harmonic is the most unstable one and though controlling the first and second order Fourier harmonicas the active stabilization (using air injection) can realize a considerable stall margin enhancement.

However, there are many barriers for the compressor active stabilization to be further applied on real engines. It is admitted that the “actuator bandwidth” is one of the critical reason. The existing results have shown that this method only effects when the stall inception is “modal wave” type, and the actuators can only generate disturbance with simple modes. Another challenge for traditional active stabilization method to be full-scale used is the costs of sensors, data process systems and actuators. It is very hard to set 4 or 8 sensors for every stage in a multi-stage compressor, let alone the complex actuations for each stage. Besides, the time between detectable stall inception and fully developed stall is too short for the control system to start the actuators. Thus, a more suitable

stability control strategy for compressor should consider adopting broadband actuators which are simpler than air injectors or adjustable vanes to suppress the stall inception and more advanced stall prediction technique to earn more available time for stability control.

Traditional casing treatments are typical passive stabilization techniques which can enhance the compressor stall margin by improving the end-wall flow via proper geometry designs. The most general insufficiencies of traditional casing treatments are the efficiency penalty and the uncertain design methodology. Inspired by the acoustic liner technique, a novel casing treatment which can supply impedance boundary condition and additional damping to the compressor system was proposed and developed [6-8]. Unlike the traditional casing treatment, this novel casing treatment effects through suppressing the nonlinear amplification of stall precursors rather than changing the flow structure. The effectiveness of this stall-precursor suppressed (SPS) casing treatment is remarkable, which has been testified on both subsonic compressor [6] and transonic compressor with uniform inlet condition and inlet distortions [9, 10]. Most experimental results have shown that the SPS casing treatment can obviously enhance the compressor stall margin without inducing additional efficiency loss at design point, but little compression capability and efficiency penalties at large flow rate. So, the optimal opportunity for applying SPS casing treatment on compressor is when and only when the compressor is operating near stall boundary. That is why a stall prediction approach is needed for constituting a close-loop control strategy.

There are many kinds of stall warning approaches based on wavelet analysis [11], Fourier analysis [12], variance analysis [13] and so on. Recently, a stall warning approach based on the correlation analysis and probability distribution analysis has been proposed [14]. It has been found that the blade signal is a periodic phenomenon, and its periodicity will be destroyed when the compressor is operating near stall. Through correlation analysis for the compressor blade signal and a further probability distribution analysis of the correlation results, the instability phenomenon could be predicted earlier than that through detecting stall inceptions.

How to establish a control strategy which can combine the SPS casing treatment and the stall warning approach is a quite challenging task. In the early 1950s, adaptive control method was proposed to solve the problem of automatic pilot in aircraft, and this concept was fast developed with the advance of computer technology during the after several decades. Similarly with the aircraft, a compressor system is also a complex system with many uncertain parameters because of the various operation states and environment situations. So this paper considers carrying out an adaptive control method to realize the compressor stabilization. In this adaptive control system, the geometrically parameterized SPS casing treatment is regarded as an adaptive controller which can suppress the stall precursors in broadband, and the stall warning approach is the primary component of the observer which can judge the compressor stability states

and instruct the controller to realize an optimal control result. This paper will introduce the technique of SPS casing treatment (its mechanism and design methodology are the major concerns) and the stall warning approach respectively. And at last, the adaptive control system for compressor stability will be established and applied on a low speed compressor.

NOMENCLATURE

P	observed output	\bar{p}_j^n	pressure signal
p'	sensor noise	N	sample number in one shaft-period
w	stochastic disturbance	n	sample number in the calculating window
o	observed parameters	$F(Rc_{th})$	cumulative distribution function for Rc
u	control input	Rc_{th}	threshold of Rc
σ	perforated ratio	$P(\bullet)$	probability
l_b	length of the back-chamber	θ	certain parameters
h_b	height of the back-chamber	x	the compressor state
Ma_b	Mach number of bias flow	$\hat{\theta}$	uncertain parameters
M	mass flow	\hat{x}	optimal state option
φ	flow coefficient		
Rc	correlation coefficient		

MAIN SCOPE

Fig. 1 Typical linear feedback control system

A typical linear feedback control system is shown in Fig. 1, the fixed control law cannot effect when the controlled device is uncertain. As mentioned in the introduction part, the adaptive control strategy was proposed to realize the optimal control for system with uncertain parameters, such as the aircrafts or the aero-engines. The most general adaptive control system is shown in Fig. 2, of which the control law is not fixed, and the control strategy is usually optimized (selected from a database or just an experiences based vague one) according to the observation about the current state of controlled device. The controlled device is usually a complex dynamic system with uncertain parameters. The parameter p is the observed output of the controlled device. Here, the effects of stochastic disturbance w and sensor noise p' to the compressor system can be also taken into consideration.

Fig. 2 The adaptive control system

When this control system is applied on the compressor, the controlled device will be the compressor system combined with its inlet and outlet parts, and the control purpose is the stability of compressor. The SPS casing treatment can be used as the system controller, and the observer consists of series sensors and the stall warning approach. The main scope for this paper is going to establish such stability control system whose function can be summarized as a flow chart, as shown in Fig. 3. The key factors for this control system are the observer module which should measure the certain parameters and estimate the uncertain parameters and the database of the control law which is built from the geometrical parameters research for SPS casing treatment. The details of these aspects will be explained in the following parts, and more basic information will be supplied in the appendix part at last.

Fig. 3 Flow chart of adaptive stability control system for compressor system

And all the experimental investigations were implemented on a low speed test compressor TA36, and the details of this test rig will be introduced in the appendix part at last of this paper.

STALL CONTROL BY IMPEDANCE WALL BOUNDARY

A. Stall-precursor suppressed (SPS) casing treatment

For the stability of a system, it is determined by the system initial and boundary conditions, and any change of the boundary condition will inevitably have effects on stability. When treating the compressor as a dynamic system, the attenuation of stall precursor waves could be accelerated by supplying additional system damping. And the impedance wall boundary condition can be regarded as the additional system for its suppressing the stall precursors. For this reason, a type of novel casing

treatment called Stall Precursor-Suppressed (SPS) casing treatment (Fig. 4) has been proposed to improve compressor stall margin. Based on the previous investigations about the effect of grazing-bias flow interaction on impedance of perforated plates [16-19], the configuration of this novel casing treatment is suggested as the one with perforated plate and annular back-chamber. For such configuration, the recirculation flow pulsed by the blade generates series unsteady shedding vortexes at the slot edge, and these shedding vortexes can interact with the pressure perturbations in the flow field. This vortex-pressure wave interaction is believed can constitute an impedance boundary condition for compressor system. And such unsteady boundary condition (or impedance boundary) caused by the recirculating flow in the casing treatment will certainly have an influence on the evolution of the initial perturbation for rotating stall (stall inceptions or any stall precursors).

Fig. 4 Sketch of vortex-wave interaction in SPS casing treatment

Under this situation, the evolution of various pressure perturbations in the flow will be certainly affected by the “soft” boundary condition, and the stability of the compressor system will be improved. The vortex-sound interaction is the fundamental of such casing treatment. Besides, theoretically, the impedance of such casing treatment can be described by the impedance models based on the understanding of the vortex wave and pressure wave interaction in the perforated configurations. And the impedance models could be contained into a compressor stability model to evaluate the effect of such casing treatment [20, 21].

B. Mechanism of SPS casing treatment

When we talk about the mechanism of traditional casing treatment, the flow structure transition of end-wall region is always involved for the recirculation flow with high momentum which can remove the tip blockage is

confirmed as the major mechanism of its effectiveness. While, as for SPS casing treatment, the stability improvement comes from the unsteady system boundary condition (damping) rather than the direct effect on the flow field. Because of the vortex wave and pressure wave interaction, the most important aspect for the stabilization mechanism of SPS casing treatment is the shedding vortices generated from the recirculation flow instead of the recirculation flow itself. And another key factor is the function of the back-chamber which can communicate each blade passage via the perforated plate. This communication can average the blade loading of every blade passage and avoid rotating stall caused by some local flow separations. Previous experimental results also showed that the back-chamber can form a circumferential mode for stall precursors, which means the energy of stall precursors is redistributed and the additional damping is supplied because of the longer propagation distance [22]. Power spectrum density (PSD) results can present the energy of pressure perturbation in the flow field. The comparison of PSD for a test compressor with and without SPS casing treatment with a proper geometric design during the pre-stall is shown in Fig. 5 [22]. The amplitude of CT case is much lower than that of SC case, which means the SPS casing treatment can obviously suppress the amplification of stall precursors.

Fig. 5 Comparison of PSD with and without SPS casing treatment pre-stall

C. Optimal design for SPS casing treatment

In our previous research [21], the work about how to construct a special casing treatment to create an unsteady boundary and how to model such boundary condition were presented, and how to predict the stall inception of subsonic and transonic compressors, especially in compressor design stage has also been discussed.

In this section, based on the previous investigations, the main work on compressor stability enhancement using SPS casing treatment will be introduced brightly, and then the theoretical research on the stall margin improvement of fan/compressors with the different geometric parameters of casing treatment will be analysed in detail.

Model of SPS Casing Treatment

As shown in Fig. 6, a linear cascade of blades is modelled by a three-dimensional semi-actuator disk composed of flat-plate foils with chord length c , spacing s and stagger angle θ . The x , y and z represent axial, circumferential and radial coordinates, respectively. This model assumes that the flow disturbances have wavelengths in its circumferential direction that are large compared with the blade spacing. There is no restriction

upon the ratio of blade chord length to wavelength. A compressible, inviscid, nonheat-conductive uniform flow is considered. As to casing walls, the hub side ($z=0$) is assumed rigid while the tip side ($z=h$, where h is the radial blade height) is assumed to have a finite acoustic impedance.

Fig. 6 Sketch map of a compressor stage unwrapped in the circumferential direction

Based on the analysis of the unsteady phenomenon caused by casing treatments, a recessed casing treatment can be modelled by radial complex eigenvalues (Fig. 7). Mathematically, the function of casing treatments has been expressed by a wall impedance condition that has been involved in the stability model through the eigenvalues and the corresponding eigenfunctions of the system. Besides, the effect of shock waves in cascade channel on the stability prediction is also considered in the present model.

Fig. 7 Diagram of a single blade row and a new type of casing treatment

Various numerical results show that the stability model can give a reasonable prediction to the stall onset point of compressors. Especially, the present experimental data also shows a good agreement with the predicting result by use of the input parameters either from the experimental measurement or from steady CFD calculation (Fig. 8).

Fig. 8 Stability prediction of a low speed test compressor at 100% design speed

Parameters Research for SPS Casing Treatment

Based on an extended stall inception model with the extrapolation hypothesis, an evaluation approach has been developed to quantitatively assess the enhancement of the stall margin during the design of such SPS casing treatment.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Fig. 9 Effect of SPS casing treatment with different configurations on stability of TA36 at design rotational speed

In the present work, for a low speed test compressor, the mean flow obtained from experimental measurement at steady state is adopted as input data of the stability model. Details of the aerodynamic parameters of the compressor are shown by Sun et al. [23].

The results of the stall margin improvement by using the SPS casing treatment on a low speed test compressor are shown in Fig. 9. The black lines are the characteristics of the test compressor without the SPS casing treatment and the others are the results for various design parameters of the SPS casing treatment, including open area ratio σ of the perforated plate, height of back-chamber h_b , length of back-chamber l_b , and Mach number of bias flow Ma_b through the perforated plate.

It is noted that for a flow stability problem, the lower order modes always tend to become unstable before the higher order modes. Therefore, in this paper, all numerical predictions will focus on how to change the most unstable mode, such as the (1, 1) mode, from unstable operating points to stable state, by setting up different parameters of the SPS casing treatment. It is found that the mass flow at the stall point without the SPS casing treatment is 5.5kg/s and the SPS casing treatments can cause varying degrees of stall margin enhancement.

The theoretical prediction of open area ratio σ on test compressor at design rotational speed is shown in Fig. 9 (a). It is seen that the SPS casing treatment with a porous wall, which has only 4% open area ratio, can extend the stable operating range of this subsonic fan. The compressor goes to stall at the mass flow of 5.25kg/s, and the stall margin enhancement of mass flow is 4.5% in comparison with the solid wall condition. With the increase of the open area ratio from 4% to 8%, the stall margin will be further improved. When the open area ratio is beyond 8%, the stall margin is not improved obviously. Thus, it is not the larger the better for the open area ratio to enhance the stall margin.

From the results of the height of back-chamber h_b shown in Fig. 9 (b), it is found that the SPS casing treatment results in obvious stall margin enhancement only when the height is larger than 5mm. Then the stall margin will be further improved with the increase of the height from 5mm to 60mm. However, the obvious stall margin enhancement does not appear when the height increases from 95mm to 115mm.

The results of the length of back-chamber l_b (open area ratio is 6%) on compressor stability are shown in Fig. 9 (c). When the back-chamber length l_b is less than 175mm, the SPS casing treatment have no effect on stall margin improvement. When l_b is more than 225mm, the stable operating range of the concerned compressor is visibly improved.

From the results of the Mach number of bias flow Ma_b shown in Fig. 9 (d), it can be seen that the stall margin does not change clearly while the Ma_b increases from 0.01 to 0.03. When Ma_b is further increased, the stall margin enhancement further decreases and the relative speed in the SPS casing treatment condition becomes lower than that in the solid wall condition.

Through this parameters research, the effectiveness trends of the SPS casing treatment with different design parameters can be obtained. And for different operating conditions, these trends would be different too. So, more abundant investigations will constitute the database of SPS casing treatment for its optimal control result aimed at different conditions.

D. Open-loop control with optimal geometric parameters

In the present research, based on the theoretical and experimental research about the sensitivity of SPS casing treatment configuration, an open loop control strategy of fan/compressor stability has been demonstrated, which has adjustable stall margin without obvious drop of performance at all working conditions. The automated equipment can regulate the geometric parameters of the SPS casing treatment, such as the volume of the back chamber and the open area ratio of the perforated plate (Fig. 10). It should be noted that when the compressors are operating far from the stall point, the slots can be completely closed to avoid changing its original characteristics.

Fig. 10 Sketch of the SPS casing treatment with adjustable parameters

The working conditions of the fan/compressor are different and the requirements of stall margin are different too. The stall margin improvement varies with the change of design parameters of SPS casing treatment at different working conditions. Thus, we need to establish the database of control law of casing treatment. Here, we try to develop two technical ways for the database, theoretical design and experimental research respectively. Fig. 11 shows the experimental results of SPS casing treatment in the low-speed compressor.

Fig. 11 Experimental results of SPS casing treatment in low-speed compressor by using open loop control

STALL WARNING APPROACH

To monitor the operating condition of the fan/compressor, a stall warning approach was developed based on the aeroacoustic principles. Here, this stall warning approach is going to be used as the primary part of the observer in the adaptive control system.

As we know, there were much different kinds of vortex structures and the vortex shedding in the blade passages of the compressor which could influence the blade circulation. The change of blade circulation could be reflected on the variation of blade force. At design point, the flow field is steady without obvious vortex shedding from the blade or tip clearance. The blade force is also steady without obvious change. When operating point of the compression system is moving toward the rotating stall

boundary, the flow structure involved in this process is very intricate, even accompanied by tip vortex shedding, shock-boundary layer interaction or flow separation on blade. These flow phenomena will lead to the change of blade circulation and reflected on the variation of blade force. As the flow is unsteady, the change of blade loading may randomly occur on certain blade. Perhaps, the loading change of a certain blade may not be enough to affect compressor performance recognizably, and the stall precursor cannot be even detected at this moment. However, based on the aeroacoustic theory, it can be recorded by the near field pressure sensor and reflected on the pressure signal. This change of blade loading may randomly occur and recover in some individual blade passages. With the approach of rotating stall, it expands to more passages and appears frequently. The blade force decreases gradually and even cannot support the pressure rise in the fan/compressor. Then compressor rotating stall may occur.

Based on this phenomenon, a stall warning approach is developed. A parameter called Rc is defined and used to reflect the change of blade loading. The definition of this parameter is in the form of:

$$Rc(j) = \frac{\bar{p}_j^n \cdot \bar{p}_{j-N}^n}{|\bar{p}_j^n| |\bar{p}_{j-N}^n|} \quad (1)$$

where Rc(j) is the value of Rc at point j, j is the index of the current simple point. The vector \bar{p}_j^n is extracted from the pressure signal which can be obtained at the casing wall near blade tip. N is the number of samples in one shaft-period and n is the number of samples in the calculating window.

Fig. 12 Calculation approach of Rc

Its cumulative distribution function $F(Rc_{th})$ is used as a criterion parameter for stall warning. It is defined as

$$F(Rc_{th}) = P(Rc \leq Rc_{th}) \quad (2)$$

where Rc_{th} is a threshold of Rc and $P(\bullet)$ is the probability. When a threshold of Rc is given, the value of $F(Rc_{th})$ can reflect whether the operating point is close to rotating stall. This approach can be used to monitor the operating condition of the compressor system. The schematic diagram is shown in Fig. 13. The immediate value of Rc can be calculated by the pressure signal. Statistical estimation is conducted on Rc within a statistical window and the probability of Rc below Rc_{th} in the statistical window can be calculated. When the value of $F(Rc_{th})$ is larger than a given warning limit, the control system can create a warning signal and trigger the stall margin enhancement system. Corresponding experimental results

are shown in Table 1. This approach can create stall warning signal much earlier than the approach of stall precursor observation.

Fig. 13 The schematic of stall-warning approach.

Table 1 Stall warning time

Approach	Stall Warning Time	Revolutions
Warning limit		
$F(Rc_{th})$	5%	4.5s
	15%	2.5s
Stall precursor	0.05s	2.5

ADAPTIVE CONTROL SYSTEM FOR COMPRESSOR STABILITY

$\theta(k)$ Parameters $\hat{\theta}(k)$ Estimated Parameters

$x(k)$ States $\hat{x}(k)$ Estimated States

Fig. 14 Adaptive control system of compressor stabilization

The strategy of this adaptive control method for compressor system is shown in Fig. 14, the "parameters identification & estimation" module and the "controller parameters calculation" module constitute the "system identification" module which can detect the system parameters and judge the system states. More importantly, the "system identification" module can estimate the uncertain parameters and give an optimal option to the controller based on the existing database. At this rate, the

effects of stochastic disturbance $w(k)$ and sensor noise $v(k)$ to the compressor system can be also taken into consideration. In this adaptive control system, there are two key aspects: one is the method of identifying and estimating all certain and uncertain parameters; the other is the database used to supply an optimal option to the controller. The first thing is guaranteed by a series of sensors to detect these certain parameters θ and the state x , and by a stall warning technology to estimate these uncertain parameters $\hat{\theta}$; the second thing is accomplished by parameter study of SPS casing treatment and by founding an optimal database based on which the computer can judge an optimal state option \hat{x} to adjust the controller.

Fig. 15 The adaptive control system on a TA36

The specific implementation scheme on a low speed compressor is shown as Fig. 15. It contains a dynamic pressure sensor mounted on the casing detecting the unsteady static pressure perturbations near the rotor tip, and the actuation unit is mainly the SPS casing treatment whose slot can be switched on and off as controller. The implementation of feedback control depends on a stall warning approach, which can through the pressure signal processing and the evaluation of the periodicity judge the stability of a compressor system. The open-loop stability control has been carried out and realized on a low speed compressor before. In this method, the observed quantity for a sensor (or we can say for the condition judge) is not the controlled quantity for the actuation unit. This factor is quite different to the traditional active control strategies. Without decomposed the perturbations into Fourier harmonic waves, the stall warning approach can nearly simultaneously do the signal process and get the probability distribution of R_c which can directly reflect the stability situation of a compressor operation point. Then, by setting a proper threshold value of the probability distribution, the control system will do the judgment of whether switch on the SPS casing treatment or not. So here the observed quantity is the probability distribution of R_c and the controlled quantity is the bandwidth perturbations which can be suppressed by the SPS casing treatment.

This strategy avoids spending time to detect the stall inception, to do the Fourier data process, and to choose a proper control strategy. Besides the stall warning approach

is also immediate to reflect the stability situation, and the servo motor can switch on the slot of SPS casing treatment really quickly. Thus, this adaptive control system can accomplish the goal of a whole feedback control process.

Experiments are conducted under 100% design speed on TA36. A sensor located on the casing in front of the rotor blade is used to sample the pressure signal. A control system software is designed to monitor the operating condition of the compressor system by calculating and monitoring the value of $F(R_{c_{th}})$ and to control the SPS casing treatment. The warning limit is set as 0.6.

EFFECTIVENESS OF ADAPTIVE CONTROL

The control results of such adaptive control system are shown in Fig. 16. The first row of the figure is the value of R_c calculated from the pressure signal. The second row is the value of $F(R_{c_{th}})$ and the third row is the value of flow coefficient. From the figure, we can see that the value of $F(R_{c_{th}})$ is near 0 when the flow coefficient is above 0.26 and begin to increase with the decrease of flow coefficient. When the value of $F(R_{c_{th}})$ goes up to 0.6, the control system triggered the SPS casing treatment and the open ratio of the perforated plate switches from 0 to the given size, which is confirmed to be the best size for stall margin enhancement under this operating condition. During this period, the value of $F(R_{c_{th}})$ begins to decrease. When the open ratio of the perforated plate reaches the target value, the value of $F(R_{c_{th}})$ decreases to about 0.16. At this moment, the open ratio of the perforated plate is switched to 0 manually and the value of $F(R_{c_{th}})$ begins to increase again. When the open ratio of the perforated plate reaches 0, value of $F(R_{c_{th}})$ increases to about 0.6 and keeps at this level. At this operating point, $F(R_{c_{th}})$ can reflects the change of the system boundary condition. When the open ratio of the perforated plate is switched to the given value, the compressor can work at the operating point with a lower flow coefficient comparing with the stall point without control.

Fig. 16 stall margin enhancement with control

More control results are shown in Fig. 17. With the throttling process, the compressor operates approaching the stall boundary and the $F(R_c)$ increases constantly, and once the $F(R_c)$ reaches the warning limit, the SPS casing

treatment will participate into the adaptive control system. Consequently, the FRc starts to decrease which means that the compressor stall margin is enhanced. Similarly, at that time, if the SPS casing treatment is closed manually, the FRc will increase again until it reach the stall warning limit for the second time and trigger the SPS casing treatment once again.

Fig. 17 The adaptive stability control result

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

Considering the dominated effects of stall inception for the evolution of rotating stall and the mechanism of SPS casing treatment, an adaptive control method for compressor stability has been proposed and developed. This presented adaptive stability control method can warn the flow instability in time via the stall warning approach and well extend the stability margin of test compressor by means of the SPS casing treatment which can suppress the stall precursors. Based on the observation, the environment parameters and the compressor status (operating parameters and stability state) can be obtained. Then the controller can adopt an optimized control law (optimal casing geometry) to realize the compressor stability control. Experimental results have shown well agreement with this statement. In addition, theoretically for this control method, the accurate stall warning and optimal geometric parameter data base are the key factors which need to be constantly improved.

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ANNEX A LOW SPEED TEST COMPRESSOR TA36

Fig. 18 Schematic of test rig and measurement arrangement

Table 2 Design Parameters for TA36 Fan

Geometrical parameters			
	Rotor		Stator
No. of blades	20		27
Tip diameter	600 mm		600 mm
Hub diameters	346mm		401mm
stagger angle at hub	45°		0°
Aerodynamic parameters			
Mass Flow	6.5kg/s	Design Speed	2900 rpm
Efficiency	85 %	Total pressure ratio at design point	1.022
Stall margin	15.5%	Static pressure rise at near stall point	2000 Pa

The present work is all performed on a low-speed test compressor TA36 on which the experimental tests under both uniform and other distorted inlet conditions have been carried out in the past few years. The schematic of this test rig is shown in Fig. 18. It contains one stage fan (Fig. 18, item 4) with one stage stator (Fig. 18, item 5). The power supply of this test rig is an AC-motor (Fig. 18, item 7) with a torque meter which can accurately measure the output power of the motor shaft and the motor is installed in the nozzle core (Fig. 18, item 10). And there is an annular throttle (Fig. 18, item 8) which can change the nozzle area by adjusting its axial position. Fig. 18 also demonstrates three cross profiles of this test rig, inlet total/static pressures are measured through a five-hole total pressure comb (Fig. 18, item 2) and four static pressure taps (Fig. 18, item 1) on the inlet casing (Fig. 18, Plane A); and outlet total/static pressures are also measured through a five-hole total pressure comb (Fig. 18, item 6) and four static pressure taps (Fig. 18, item 11) on the outlet casing (Fig. 18, Plane C). Besides, 8 high-frequency response Kulite sensors are mounted in the casing wall near the rotor tip (Fig. 18, Plane B) to detect the static pressure perturbations. Some main design parameters of TA36 compressor are shown in Table 2. A NI-PXI system is the main data acquisition system which contains 48 acquisition channels, and its maximum sampling rate is 100 kHz. The controllable bleed valve of TA36 rig enables the operation point to approach the pre-stall region slowly and move away from stall quickly. So this set up makes sure that all the steady-state operating characteristics of the compressor can be obtained by the standard time-mean instruments used in the present work.